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Research Article

A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY FAMILY-BASED FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH OVERWEIGHT AND OBESITY

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Introduction: Globally at least 20 million children under the age of 5 years were estimated to be overweight in the year 2005 and studies on childhood obesity prevalence of obesity ranging from 5% to 20% in various settings.

Objectives of the study: The main objective of this study was to analyze the family-based factors associated with overweight and obesity.

Material and methods: This cross sectional study was conducted in the Government and private schools of Lahore during 2017 to 2018. A stratified, multistage cluster sample of 1860 children aged five to twelve years in twelve primary schools of City District Lahore was enrolled. The sampling design has been used previously in nutritional assessment surveys.

Results: Children whose parents were having college (23%) or higher (29%) education had significantly higher risk of being overweight and obese ($P < 0.001$) as compared to children whose parents were illiterate (3%) and educated up to high school (10%). Overweight and obesity were significantly higher among children with parents having higher education among both boys and girls (both $P < 0.001$). Children whose both parents were working (22.5%) were significantly more likely to be overweight and obese ($P = 0.002$) than those whose mother was a housewife (15.5%).

Conclusion: It is concluded that family-based factors were significantly associated with overweight and obesity among school-aged children in Pakistan. Obesity prevalence was highest among boys, children living with middle-income families and those in the younger age groups.

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INTRODUCTION:

Globally at least 20 million children under the age of 5 years were estimated to be overweight in the year 2005 and

studies on childhood obesity prevalence of obesity ranging from 5% to 20% in various settings. Changing dietary patterns, sedentary lifestyles and a decline in physical activity are believed to contribute to the global obesity epidemic among both adults and children. Although, the subject of obesity has already received some attention in Pakistan, the subject of obesity among children has only recently gained attention. Pakistan has an estimated prevalence of childhood obesity between 15% to 20%. The proportion of obese and overweight children in Karachi was found to be 6% and 19% respectively [1].

Obesity is a global epidemic and children are the worst affected with an estimated ten percent of school-aged children being overweight and one quarter of these being obese worldwide. The 2004 World Health Assembly at Geneva called for specific action to halt the epidemic that is now penetrating the developing countries including Pakistan, especially in the affluent urban population [2]. Childhood obesity adversely affects physiological and psychosocial well-being, results in cardiovascular and metabolic diseases, leads to increased mortality and morbidity, and causes heavy health expenditures and reduced social status. Targeted interventions for the prevention of childhood obesity, tailored to local circumstances and involving communities, should begin early in life [3].

Influence of family environment and parental characteristics has important consequences regarding childhood obesity and it should be considered in designing policies and interventions. Globally, the relationship between childhood obesity and family-based factors, including parental education, parental working status, siblings, persons in child's living room, smoking in living space and neighborhood income level has been extensively explored [4]. However, most studies are conducted in the developed countries and literature is scarce in this regard among South Asian children. There is no data on association of family-based factors with overweight and obesity among school-aged children in Pakistan. The study aimed to explore family-based factors associated with overweight and obesity among Pakistani primary school children [5].

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study was to analyze the family-based factors associated with overweight and obesity.

Material and methods

This cross sectional study was conducted in the Government and private schools of Lahore during 2017 to 2018. A stratified, multistage cluster sample of 1860 children aged five to twelve years in twelve primary schools of City District Lahore was enrolled. The sampling design has been used previously in nutritional assessment surveys. Stratified sampling, based on the population and educational system characteristics, was used to have proportionate representation of gender, area of residence and socioeconomic status (SES). The list of all public and private primary schools in Lahore was provided by the Punjab Department of Education. The listed schools were stratified according to the geographic area and monthly fee structure of schools into following four strata: a) urban with high SES.

Data Collection

The sampled schools were visited on pre-arranged dates in summer 2017 by a team of trained senior medical students lead by the Principal Investigator. Health education of children and teachers was also carried out after data collection in the respective school. Analogue physician health scales, standardized before the examination, were used.

Statistical analysis

The data of respiratory function were compared between the smoker and non-smoker groups using the independent t-test for normally distributed data or the Mann-Whitney U test for other distributions. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS:

Children whose parents were having college (23%) or higher (29%) education had significantly higher risk of being overweight and obese ($P < 0.001$) as compared to children whose parents were illiterate (3%) and educated up to high school (10%). Overweight and obesity were significantly higher among children with parents having higher education among both boys and girls (both $P < 0.001$). Children whose both parents were working (22.5%) were significantly more likely to be overweight and obese ($P = 0.002$) than those whose mother was a housewife (15.5%). Overweight and obesity were 9% among children having more than three siblings that significantly increased to 23% among children having one to three siblings and 35% among children having no sibling ($P < 0.001$).

Table 01: Family-based factors associated with overweight among Pakistani primary school children

	Total	Thin	Normal	Overweight	Obese	Significance	
Family-based factors	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	χ^2	P value
Parental education							
Illiterate	366 (19.7)	163 (44.5)	193 (52.7)	8 (2.2)	02 (0.5)	161.56	< 0.001
High school	496 (26.7)	193 (38.9)	255 (51.4)	33 (6.7)	15 (3.0)		
College	531 (28.5)	142 (26.7)	268 (50.5)	66 (12.4)	55 (10.4)		
Higher education	467 (25.1)	103 (22.1)	227 (48.6)	69 (14.8)	68 (14.6)		
Parental working status							
Father only	1465 (78.8)	496 (33.9)	742 (50.6)	125 (8.5)	102 (7.0)	14.32	0.002
Both parents	395 (21.2)	105 (26.6)	201 (50.9)	51 (12.9)	38 (9.6)		
Persons in child's living room							

No	116 (6.2)	24 (20.7)	48 (41.4)	28 (24.1)	16 (13.8)	77.84	< 0.001
1-3	791 (42.5)	212 (26.8)	420 (53.1)	86 (10.9)	73 (9.2)		
> 3	953 (51.2)	365 (38.3)	475 (49.8)	62 (6.5)	51 (5.4)		
Smoking in living place							
Yes	546 (29.4)	194 (35.5)	263 (48.2)	52 (9.5)	37 (6.8)	4.04	0.731
No	1314 (70.6)	407 (31.0)	680 (51.8)	124 (9.4)	103 (7.8)		

DISCUSSION:

A high prevalence of overweight and obesity among the study (8% and 12% respectively) was an important finding of our study. The prevalence of obesity was higher among boys than girls (15% and 8% respectively). The high prevalence of overweight and obesity is one of the most important causes of childhood obesity [6]. As the study was taken from a typical and developed world of the largest cities of Pakistan the findings of the study can be generalized to similar population groups.

This prevalence of obesity among these schoolchildren is consistent with, or even higher than, similar studies in other regions of the world. For instance, the prevalence of obesity among children in the Netherlands aged 3-16 years was 13.1% and 10.7% among boys and girls respectively [7]. In a study in Vietnam the prevalence of overweight and obesity is estimated to be 20.5% and 16.3% respectively and these figures are similar to bear [8]. In most of these studies the boys were more likely to be overweight and obese than girls. The higher risk of overweight and obesity in boys in the multivariate model was highly statistically significant. In developing countries overweight and obesity is a phenomenon among affluent and mostly urban societies. For instance, a recent publication

from the National Family Health Surveys (1992 to 2006) showed that these are more likely to be obese than those in the lower income groups. BMI are more likely to have low self-esteem and less satisfaction with their bodies than with their academic achievement [9]. The results of our study also showed a similar trend. For instance, children who rated themselves as poor athletes were 5.50 times more likely to be obese than those who rated themselves excellent athletes. We also had 7.75 times more likely to be obese. Other studies have shown that obese children are more aware of their weight status and a higher proportion of them [10].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that family-based factors were significantly associated with overweight and obesity among school-aged children in Pakistan. Obesity prevalence was highest among boys, children living with middle-income families and those in the younger age groups. The determinants of obesity can be found in the home and school environment. Children who have been poor in their lives are likely to be uncomfortable, indicating that they are uncomfortable. Finally, the consumption of fruits and vegetables is an indicator of healthier eating in daily life. Parents, schools, education

department,

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